

Aging Art in VR: Conservators on Trust, Risk, and Digital Futures

How do art conservators evaluate virtual reality tools that simulate the aging of paintings? This interview series explores professional perspectives on trust, uncertainty, expertise, and the role of human-centered technology in cultural heritage conservation. In this conversation, conservator Franziska Marinovic reflects on the opportunities and challenges of using immersive simulation technologies to support conservation practice and decision-making.

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Katharina Flicker (KF): What does your work with oil paintings look like, particularly in relation to predicting aging processes? What tools and methods are typically used?

Franziska Marinovic (FM): It varies from case to case. Usually, we begin with a visual examination. First, we inspect the painting as closely as possible with the naked eye, looking for signs of damage and indicators of aging. We also employ imaging techniques ranging from visible light and ultraviolet light to infrared examination, which can, for example, reveal the structure of the layers.

Invasive methods, such as taking a sample for cross-section, are used only rarely and when there is a strong justification. In many cases, however, this is not necessary.

KF: Against this background, how could a VR tool that simulates the aging of oil paintings support your work?

FM: In the context of my work in a museum, I would most likely use such a

tool as a means of visualization for colleagues who are not trained in conservation, such as exhibition managers, collection managers, or exhibition designers.

These colleagues often approach our department with questions regarding how long a particular work may be displayed under certain environmental conditions. We already work according to clearly defined guidelines, but a tool like this could provide valuable visual support. In other words, it could help demonstrate what might happen to an oil painting if environmental requirements are not met.

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As a freelance conservator, I could also imagine using such a tool in a similar way.

It could also be beneficial in teaching, helping to further illustrate to students in relevant courses how specific preventive conservation measures can influence the ageing of an artwork.

KF: Would such a tool also be useful in the context of actual conservation treatments?

FM: In that case, the threshold for using it would be significantly higher. However, I can imagine advantages such as being able to examine an art work from all angles, compare pictures showing different stages of aging, or illustrate the importance of preventive conservation measures. The question remains whether VR would actually be necessary for this purpose and whether such technology would be adopted in our field if VR headsets were not readily available.

KF: So far, we have focused on the potential benefits and applications of such a tool. Do you have any concerns about using a VR tool to simulate aging processes in this context?

FM: We sometimes encounter unrealistic expectations among non-specialists regarding what conservation can achieve. I am concerned that a tool like this – especially if it allows users to visualize what a painting may once have looked like – could create expectations that this state could be achieved through the right treatment.

On the other hand, such a tool might also help address this problem by communicating more effectively that features such as craquelure are part of a

painting's aging process and history, and do not diminish its value.

KF: What criteria would such a tool need to meet for you to consider the simulated aging process credible and realistic?

FM: Transparency, documentation, and personal professional experience are all important. If the results are based on empirical data that I can verify, if there is a scientific foundation explaining how the tool was developed and why a painting is predicted to evolve in a particular way over time, and if there are scientific publications supporting its methodology, then I could certainly imagine using it.

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Most importantly, I have my own professional experience and can assess how an aging process would be expected to unfold. If the tool's results contradicted my professional experience, I would probably distrust it and choose not to use it.

Julian Salhofer (JS): Would a lack of transparency – that is, not knowing how the tool arrives at its results – affect your trust in the simulation? Or would the tool already be trustworthy to you as long as its results aligned with your own experience and observations?

FM: In everyday life, we place trust in many technical systems without fully understanding how they function. If the results of such a tool corresponded with

my own professional experience, I would initially assume that the simulation had been developed on a sound professional basis. In that case, detailed background information might be less important to me. However, the situation would be different if the results presented by the tool did not appear consistent with my observations or professional knowledge.

KF, JS: Thank you very much for the interview.

Franziska Marinovic studied Conservation with a specialization in Paintings and Polychrome Wooden Sculptures at the University of Applied Arts Vienna. During her studies, she gained practical experience through her work in numerous museums and conservation studios. Following graduation, she served as a University Assistant at the institute from 2011 to 2013. She also participated in international conservation projects, including conservation campaigns in Patan, Nepal, and the conservation of archaeological burial finds in Luxor, Egypt. Since 2023, she has been working in the conservation workshop of the Österreichische Galerie Belvedere in Vienna.